

STUDY ON MARKETING AND CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR SYNGENTA PRODUCT AMPLIGO IN HOSHIARPUR DISTRICT OF PUNJAB

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Abstract

Syngenta India Ltd. Is a leading company in Fungicide marketing in Punjab, there are 23 districts and 5 Divisions in Punjab state and the divisions are Jalandhar, Ferozpur, Faridkot and Rupnagar. Punjab was selected, and under this Jalandhar division we selected the Hoshiarpur district purposively for the present study on the basis of the maximum area under sugarcane cultivation. The district has an area of 3365 km². The district has a population density of 683 inhabitants per square Kilometre (1,770/sq mi). The Study of Consumer Behavior has become essential. Consumers are the kings of markets. Without consumers no business organization can run. All the activities of the business concerns end with consumers and consumer satisfaction. Customer behavior study is based on consumer buying the quality of the product, brand reputation, performance and long durability effect of fungicide are the main attributes which are preferred by farmers at the time of purchasing of selected fungicide in the study area. Consumer buying behavior has become an integral part of strategic market planning. Market Strategies are formulated to provide superior customer value. In formulating market strategies, the 4 Ps are directed at the target market.

Key words: Fungicide, Syngenta, Ampligo, Marketing and Consumer Buying behavior

Introduction

Agriculture continues to be the mainstay to India's large and growing population for its sustained food security. More than 70 percent people are engaged in agriculture sector. The sector provides employment to over half of country's work force and is the single largest private sector occupation. Due to the prominence of agriculture in the national food security and the employment, its performance is of great focus in the India's policy and planning. The contributory share of agriculture in GDP was 55.4 percent in 1950-51, 52 percent in 1960-61 and is reduced to 13.7 percent only in 2012-13. Moreover, the Indian agriculture is characterized by dominance of the small and marginal farmers having very small land holdings. Majority of the people belong to farming communities. It provides food and raw materials to the small scale and cottage industries who's are directly dependent on agriculture.

Fungicides prevent and cure diseases which can have adverse effects on crop yields and quality. The main markets are fruit and vegetables, cereals and rice. Plant diseases are caused by a great variety of pathogens. This requires many products used in combination or series to control the full range of problems in ways that minimize the chance of resistance building up. During recent years, among few new active ingredients, an innovative generation of fungicides - strobilurins - has been developed and introduced in order to improve the control in the key plant diseases like downy mildew, powdery mildew, late blight, rychnosporium, net blotch and eyespot. The knowledge of general characteristics of the study area is essential for understanding the features of the area. This will facilitate the discussion with respect to similarities and variation in land use pattern, rainfall, cropping pattern etc. This also enlightens the socio-economic conditions of the area selected for the study.

While Syngenta generally maintains multiple sources of supply and obtains supplies of raw materials from a number of countries, there are a limited number of instances where Syngenta has entered into single-source supply contracts or where Syngenta routinely makes spot purchases from a single supplier in respect of active ingredients, intermediates or raw materials for certain important products. These instances occur where there is sufficient commercial benefit and security of supply can be assured, or where there is no viable alternative source of supply. Such single supplier arrangements account for approximately 16 percent of Syngenta's purchases of active ingredients, intermediates and raw materials used in Crop Protection products, as determined by cost. Syngenta's ability to obtain sufficient amounts of those materials may be adversely affected by the unforeseen loss of a supplier or from a supplier's

inability to meet its supply obligations. The percentage of single supplier arrangements could increase in the future if consolidation were to occur among multiple supply sources. Syngenta Pvt. Ltd. created and produced Ampligo. To combat the Cotton bug Pink Wall Worm, Ampligo was initially registered as "Fullswing." Ampligo was introduced in India in 2015. Known By: Ampligo Known as: Ampligo Ingredients: 150 ZC.

Total area of Hoshiarpur district is 339000 hectares, out of which forest area is 109000 hectares (32.15 per cent). Nearly 60 percent is the net sown area out of which 81 percent is irrigated and the cropping intensity is 170 percent, 18 percent points less than the state average. For 90 percent of irrigated area, source of irrigation is tubewells (electric operated) and wells. Topographically, the district can be divided into three broad regions on the basis of soil-croplime complex. Introduction: The first region is constituted by flood plains comprising Dasuya, Tanda and Mukerian blocks. This is the most fertile area of the district covering onefourth of the geographical area. It has wide spread irrigational facilities. Paddy, wheat, maize and sugarcane are the main crops of this region. A lot of soil and water conservation activities like rain water harvesting structures, harvesting of base flow and micro lift systems for irrigation, rain water recharging structures have been done and have shown very good results. The third region comprises Hoshiarpur-1, Mahilpur and Garhshankar blocks located on the beds of lower Shivalik, these are undulating plains with relatively low slope decreasing up to 4meters per kilometer. This belt also faces water shortage. This area is suitable for maize, Sugarcane and paddy crops. Of late, Ampligo sunflower/maize cropping pattern has emerged in a vast area of this region. The major horticulture crops in the district are Kinnow & other citrus fruits Mango, Guava, Peach and Grapes etc. The predominant economic activities include agricultural farming, dairying, poultry farming, horticulture, mushroom cultivation, bee keeping, ban making and other village and cottage industries handicrafts production and export thereof, transport, service activities and trade and business. There is increasing demand for new activities such as Vermiculture, beekeeping, Turmeric cultivation, Amla cultivation etc. The district is emerging as a honey bowl.

Materials and Methods

As per the stated objective of the study, suitable methods of the study were designed. This chapter was formulated as:

Study Area

Hoshiarpur district is located in the north-east part of the State. It falls in the Jalandhar Revenue Division and is situated in the Bist Doab, Doaba region of the State. The district is sub mountainous and

stretches of river Beas in the north-west. It lies between north latitude 30 degree-9 and 32 degree-05 and east longitude 75degree -32 and 76degree -12'. It shares common boundaries with Kangra and Una districts of Himachal Pradesh in the north east, Jalandhar and Kapurthala districts (interspersed) in southwest and Gurdaspur district in the north-west. At present, it has an area of 3386 Sq. Kms. and a population, as per 2011 Census is 15,86,625 persons.

Selection of respondents:

From the selected village list of all the sugarcane cultivators obtained from the village development office in each selected village. For the selection of cultivators from families were listed and 20 farmers were randomly selected from each village and then farmers were classified in to Five groups.

Table 1: Distribution of selected Hoshiarpur growers in tanda block

S. No.	Size Group	Total No. of Growers	No. of selected growers
1	Marginal farmers	80	25
2	Small farmers	120	20
3	Semi Med. farmers	150	25
4	medium farmers	180	35
5	Large farmers	70	15
	Total	600	120

Thus sample of 120 Sugarcane growers were selected for the present study.

Results And Discussion

Study on Marketing and Consumer Buying Behavior of Syngenta Product Ampligo in Hoshiarpur District of Punjab" is the title of the current study. Data must be processed and evaluated after collection

in accordance with the guidelines established for the purpose while creating the study plan. This is crucial for a research-based project study to ensure that we have the necessary data for the comparison and analysis we're planning.

Table 1 Indicated that there were 40, 45, and 35 farms in each of the three major categories of farms: small, medium, and big. A total of 120 farming groups were chosen for the investigation.

S. No.	Particulars	marginal	Small	Size of Farms Group			Average Sample
				Semi Medium	Medium	Large	
1	Size of Farms Group (in numbers)	25	20	25	35	15	120 (100.00)
2	The average size of cultivated land Holdings hectares	2.5	1.3	2.1	1.03	1.07	1.60
3	Land utilization in different crops (sown area in ha)						
	Kharif						
	Paddy	0.36	0.67	0.69	0.83	1.33	0.78
	Sugarcane	0.28	0.89	0.92	0.53	0.83	0.51
I	Maize	0.13	0.65	0.67	0.38	0.68	0.37
	Rabi						
	Wheat	0.31	0.64	0.68	0.87	1.2	0.74
	Gram	0.22	0.61	0.63	0.83	1.15	0.69
II	Mustard	0.19	0.56	0.58	0.7	1.13	0.63
	Zaid (summer)						
III	Cucumber	0.15	0.4	0.7	0.63	0.75	0.48
	Vegetables	0.13	0.3	0.5	0.55	0.6	0.40
4	Total sown area	4.27	6.08	4.57	4.48	7.81	4.43
5	Cropping intensity	266.667	251.768	251.678	273.700	281.261	265.04

Table 2 Consumer perception and buying behavior

Parameter	No. of farmers	Farmers %
Quality	29	24.17
Price	10	8.33
Packaging	6	5.00
Relation with Dealer	37	30.83
Brand Image	18	15.00
Promotional Strategies	12	10.00
Source of Information	8	6.67
Total	120.00	100.00
Marketing Channel		
Direct Sales	35	35%
Agricultural Retailers	45	45%
Online Platforms	20	20%
Total	100	100%
Brand awareness of Ampligo		

Have not heard about it	26	21.67
Have heard about it but never used	42	35.00
Seen result in other farmers field	8	6.67
Used it	44	36.67
Total	120	100

It is founded that about 24.17% farmers prefers to buy a product according to its quality, about 8.33% farmers prefers the price of product, about 05% farmers prefers the attractiveness of the packaging, 30.83% farmers buy agrochemicals only because of the relationship with the distributor, 15% of the farmers buy agro products on the basis of Brand Image, about 10% farmers buys agroproducts by convinced through promotional strategies, and 6.67% farmers take information about products from their friends and neighbors or any other person. Survey on the awareness of Syngenta products brings about an interesting aspect of farmer shearing about it, knowing about it and still not using it. The most popular marketing channel for Ampligo in Hoshiarpur District is through agricultural retailers with 45% of respondents indicating that they purchase the

product through this channel. Direct sales also had a significant share of 35%, while online platforms accounted for 20% of sales. This suggests that agricultural retailers are an important distribution channel for Ampligo in the district. However, the brand could also benefit from increasing its online presence to tap into the growing e-commerce market in the region.

By interviewing and observation it was seen that out of 120 farmer 36.67% percent of surveyed population is using whereas other 35% of farmers have either heard about it or have seen its results in their peer group. Yes apart from these, there are still 21.67% of population have not heard about the product, and 6.67% of farmers have seen results in peer field.

Table 3 Advertisement mode adopted by company

Advertise mode adopted by company	No. of Respondents	% age
Posters	33	27.50
News Paper	8	6.67
Paintings	28	23.33
Pamphlets	12	10.00
Seminar	10	8.33
Television	8	6.67
Other	21	17.50
Total	120.00	100.00
Advertise effective for agrochemicals		
Yes	85	70.83
No	35	29.17
Total	120	100
Seen Advertise of Syngenta		
Yes	98	81.67
No	22	18.33
Total	120	100

This table indicates a mode of advertisement that company adopted at the time of Promotion. A majority (i.e., 27.50%) of farmers were said that Poster, 23.33% said that painting, 10.00% said that Pamphlets, 8.33% said that seminar, 17.50% said that other like demonstration, farmers meeting etc, and 6.67% said that television. This table indicate a respondents feel advertise is effective for agro

chemical products. A majority (i.e., 70.83%) of respondent feel that advertise is effective for agrochemical products and 29.17% respondent did not feel that advertise is effective for agro chemicals. This Table shows how many respondent seen advertise of Syngenta Pvt. Ltd. A 81.67% farmer are said that they are seen advertise of Syngenta Pvt. Ltd. and only 18.33 % farmer not seen advertise.

Table 4: Marketing cost, marketing margin and price spread of Ampligo in different Size of Farms group

Sr.No.	Description	₹ /ql.	%
1	Producer's sale price	600	
2	Expenses borne by the producer	155	(25.83%)
i.	Cost of packaging	10	(1.42%)
ii.	Cost of Transportation	40	(6.66%)
iii.	Grading, filling, stitching, etc.	25	(3.57%)
iv.	Loading and Unloading	10	(1.42%)
v.	Miscellaneous cost (carry bags)	20	(2.85%)
vi.	Miscellaneous expenses	50	(7.14%)
3	Net price received by the producer	445	(74.16%)
4	Consumer's purchase price	600	(100%)
5	Price spread	155	(25.83%)
6	Producer's share in consumer's rupee (%)		74.16
7	Marketing efficiency		3.87

Table 4 reveals that average marketing cost when producers sold their product to customer in the market was ₹ 600/ql.. Among these cost

of packing ₹ 10.00/ql., Grading, Filling, Stitching, etc was ₹ 25.00/ql., loading and unloading cost ₹ 10.00/ql., transportation

cost ₹ 40.00/ql., miscellaneous expenses ₹ 50.00/ql., packing material was ₹ 20.00/ql. The total Price spread was ₹ 155.00/qt, producer's share in consumer's rupee 74.16 and market efficiency was 3.87% respectively

Table 5: Marketing Cost, Marketing Margin and Price Spread of Ampligo in different Size of Farms group

Sr.No	Description	₹ / ql.	%
1	Producer sale price to Retailer	550	
2	Cost incurred by the producer		
i.	Cost of gunny bag	20.00	(2.40%)
ii.	Grading, Filling	20.00	(2.40%)
iii.	Load & Transportation cost	40.00	(4.80%)
iv.	Cold storage charge	180.00	(21.63%)
v.	Unloading charges	10.00	(1.20%)
vi.	Total cost incurred by producer(i-v)	270.00	(32.45%)
3	Net price received by producer	280.00	(33.65%)
4	Sale price of producer to Village Merchant/Retailers	550.00	
5	Cost incurred by the Retailer		
i.	Transportation cost	40.00	(4.80%)
ii.	Labour	10.00	(1.20%)
iii.	Rent of the shop	12.00	(1.44%)
iv.	Loss, wastage and spoilage	50.00	(6.00%)
v.	Miscellaneous charges	30.00	(3.60%)
vi.	Market fee	20.00	(2.40%)
vii.	Total cost incurred	162.00	(19.47%)
6	Village Merchant/Retailer Margin	120.00	(14.42%)
7	Sale price of Retailer to Consumer	832.00	
8	Price spread (Total Marketing cost + Margin)	282.00	(38.89%)
9	Producer's share in consumer's rupee	50.90	
10	Marketing Efficiency	2.95	

Note: figure in the parenthesis indicate percentage to the total consumer price

Table 5 reveals that average marketing cost when producers sold their product to village Retailers in the market was ₹ 550.00/ql. Among these Grading, Filling, Stitching, etc was ₹ 25.00/ql., loading and Transportation cost ₹ 50.00/ql., uploading charges ₹ 10/ql. and cold storage charge ₹ 180/ql. The Average marketing cost sold to their produce through villageretailersto the consumers, was observed 32.45

%, among these costs transportation was the most important 4.80 %, followed by loss, wastage and spoilage 6.00 %, rent of the shop 1.44 %,labour 1.20 % and miscellaneous cost 3.60 % respectively. The total price spread was ₹ 282/ql., producer's share in consumer's rupee 50.90 and market efficiency was 2.95 % respectively

Table 6 : Marketing Cost, Marketing Margin, and Price Spread of Ampligo in different Sizes of Farms Group

Sr.No	Description	₹ /ql.	Percentage
1	Producer sale price to Commission agent	500.00	
2	Cost incurred by the producer		
i.	Cost of gunny bag	25.00	(2.48%)
ii.	Grading, filling	25.00	(2.48%)
iii.	Load &Transportation cost	40.00	(3.98)
iv.	Unloading charges	30.00	(0.99)
v.	Commission	70	(6.96%)
vi.	Total cost (i-viii)	190.00	(18.90%)
3	Net price received by producer	310.0	(30.84%)
4	Sale price of producer to Commission agent	500.00	
5	Cost incurred by the producer		
i.	Market fee	10.00	(0.99%)
ii.	Losses &Miscellaneous charges	120	(11.94%)
iii.	Total cost incurred by Commission agent (i-v)	130	(12.93%)

6	Commission agent Margin	110	(10.94%)
7	Sale price of Commission agent to Retailers	630	
8	Cost incurred by the Retailers	395	(39.30%)
i.	Transportation cost	40	(3.98%)
ii.	Labour	15	(1.49%)
iii.	Rent of the shop	10	(0.99%)
iv.	Loss, wastage and spoilage	150	(14.92%)
v.	Miscellaneous charges	180	(17.91%)
9	Retailers Margin	110.00	(10.94%)
10	Sale price of Retailers to consumer	1005	
11	Price spread (Total Marketing Cost + producing cost)	505	(50.59%)
12	Producer's share in consumer's rupee	34.82	
13	Marketing Efficiency	1.99	

Note: Figure in the parenthesis indicate percentage to the total consumer price

Table 6 reveals that marketing cost, marketing margin, and price spread for channel-III is important because lots of farms i.e. 82.32 % of growers preferring sale of their produce through this channel. Two intermediaries were identified through which Ampligo reaches to the consumer's i.e. commission agents, Retailers. This is identified as the longest channel. The producer sells his produce to the commission agent, who in turn sells it to retailers in the market. Finally the produce reaches to consumers after collecting margin. Average marketing cost when producers sold their produce to commission agents in the market was ₹ 150/ql. Among these cost of gunny bag ₹ 25/ql., Grading, Filling, Stitching, etc was ₹ 25.00/ql., loading and

transportation cost ₹ 40.00/ql., uploading charges ₹ 30/ql., commission charges ₹ 70/ql. respectively. The net price received by the producer was ₹ 310.00/ql. Sale price of the producer to commission agents was ₹ 500/ql. respectively. In these channel marketing cost of the producer, commission agents and retailers was 14.93 %, 12.92 % and 39.30 % of consumers paid price respectively. The commission agent margin was estimated to be 10.94 % and the retailer's margin was 10.94 % of the consumer paid price. Producer's share in consumer's rupee was 30.84 % respectively. Price spread was ₹ 505.00/ql. indifferent size of farms groups. The marketing efficiency is 1.99 % and it is low compared to the channel I and II.

Table 7: Estimation of Total Marketing Cost and Marketing Margin of Ampligo in different Size of Farms group

Sr. No	Description	Channel I	Channel II	Channel III
1	Total marketing cost	155.00	432.00	675.00
2	Total marketing margins	00.00	120.00	220.00
3	Price spread	155.00	282.00	505.00
4	Producer's share in consumer's rupee in percentage	74.16	50.90	34.82
5	Marketing efficiency in %	3.87	2.95	1.99

Table 7 reveals that total marketing cost, marketing margin, price spread, and producer's share in consumer's rupee and marketing efficiency in the marketing channels. The total market cost was higher in channel III (₹ 675.00) compared to channel II (₹ 432.00) and channel I (₹ 155.00). And the total marketing margin and price spread

was also seen higher in channel III (₹ 220.00 and ₹ 505.00) because in the channel III there are two intermediaries where as in the channel II there is only one intermediate. The producer's share in consumer's rupee was higher in channel I, 74.16%. The marketing efficiency was higher in channel I, 3.87%.

Table 11: Problems faced by respondents in use of pesticide:

S.N.	Constraints for marketing of pesticide	Respondent	
		Mean value	Rank
1	Unawareness about hazardous effect of agrochemical on human health	28	I
2	Lack of technical guidance	27.6	II
3	Poor quality of pesticide	26.8	III
4	Lack of pesticide application equipment	24.8	IV
5	Lack of easy availability	13.7	V
Constraints for use of pesticide			
1	Lack of latest recommended	34.5	I
2	How do you mix pesticides	33.25	II
3	Do you use safety measures	30.75	III
4	Disposal of empty pesticide containers	24.25	IV

Note: Figure in the parenthesis indicate the mean value and ranking of constraints.

28% respondents said that, there is lack of hazardous effect of agrochemical on human health ranked.

27.6% respondents thought that, there is lack of technical guidance for pesticides application in the region.

26.8% respondents having issue with poor quality of pesticide.

24.8% respondents thought that, there is Lack of pesticide application equipment.

13.7% respondents having least problem with Lack of easy availability. This are major problems faced by the growers during purchase of pesticide.

Conclusion

Insecticides have a bright future both now and in the future, since their use grows substantially each year. Farmers rely on pesticides, as seen by the increase in insecticide consumption. Farmers use pesticides efficiently because they don't want to waste time on the field and want rapid solutions to any problems that arise. Farmers continue to use pesticides and PGR because they produce greater crops as a consequence. On the target organisms, insecticide operates fast and with minimal effort. Most farmers use excessive amounts of pesticides, however some argue that this is harmful to the field and that they only use insecticides when absolutely essential for the crop. Insecticides are essential for farming since, according to farmers, it is

now impossible to produce crops well without them because they are attacked at every stage by various soil-specific insects. Every farmer seeks a large return on a small investment, and they employ PGRs to achieve this. PGR supplies the plant with all of its micronutrients and controls the growth of the specific plant. Overall, Syngenta's performance is strong, but it needs to engage in more successful marketing campaigns in the Hoshiarpur region. Syngenta has a significant opportunity to increase its market share in the area by increasing its promotional activities and focusing on new products. Syngenta has a great reputation in the area for customer service and a positive brand image. It must actively promote these attributes in order to increase market share and income.

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